

**STUDY OF THE STRUCTURAL INFLUENCE ON THE COMPARATIVE
SOLUBILITY OF WATER-SOLUBLE POLYSACCHARIDES ISOLATED
FROM THE FUNGUS INNONOTUS HISPIDUS GROWING IN THE
TERRITORY OF UZBEKISTAN.**

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ABSTRACT: A study was conducted on the influence of monosaccharide structure on the specific solubility of water-soluble polysaccharides obtained from *Innonotus hispidus* basidiomycetes, a fungus belonging to the Hymenochetaceae family growing on mulberry trees in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The raw materials were deresinated, purified, and re-extracted with water. The ratio of solubility in various solvents was determined, with the highest solubility observed in the ratio of Arabinose and Xylose compounds, reaching 12.5%. These studies will serve as a basis for further investigation of the biological activity of this object and its application in medicine and pharmaceuticals.

Keywords: *Innonotus hispidus*, extraction, monosaccharides, solubility, polysaccharides

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Water-soluble polysaccharide extraction was carried out in the following stages:

To extract water-soluble polysaccharides, the defatted raw material was dried to remove solvent odors, weighed, and extracted three times in a hot water bath with a reflux condenser (total ratio of raw material to extractor 1:4, 1:3, 1:2). The total duration of the three extractions was 6 hours. The obtained aqueous extracts were combined and re-evaporated in a film evaporator at a temperature ranging from 50°C to 1/5 of the initial volume, then filtered. Water-soluble polysaccharides were isolated from the obtained concentrate by adding a four-fold volume of 95% ethyl alcohol and storing at -5°C for 12 hours. After centrifugation, the precipitate was separated, washed with ethyl alcohol in a glass filter, and dried at 30°C [1].

To extract pectin substances from basidiomycetes, after water extraction, an extract was obtained using a 1.1% hydrochloric acid solution (1:10) at 95°C (water bath) for 2 hours. The extract was filtered through a nylon cloth, evaporated, dialyzed in water, and centrifuged (10 min, 6000 rpm). It was then evaporated again and precipitated with alcohol. The resulting precipitate was separated by centrifugation (6000 rpm, 10 min) and dried with alcohol. The product was washed in running water until the pH was neutralized.

The alkaline extraction of basidiomycetes was performed with a 1% sodium hydroxide solution (1:10) at a temperature of 30°C (oil bath) for 3-4 hours. The extract was filtered through a nylon cloth, centrifuged, and neutralized with acetic acid to a pH of 7.5. The extract was evaporated in a rotating film evaporator at 50°C. It was then dialyzed, frozen, and dried [2]. The food is washed in running water until the pH is neutralized

The alkaline portion of basidiomycetes was treated with a 1% sodium hydroxide solution (1:10) at a temperature of 30°C (oil bath) for 3-4 hours. The extract was filtered through a nylon cloth, centrifuged, and neutralized with acetic acid to a pH of 7.5. The extract was evaporated in a rotating film evaporator at 50°C. It was dialyzed, frozen, and dried.[2]

Determining the solubility of the sample. The weighted portion of the samples weighing 0.5 g was placed in a 100 ml conical flask and filled with 50 ml of distilled water. The flask is shaken for 2 hours, then the solution is filtered through a Schott filter (the pore size is 160 μm, previously adjusted to constant weight). After immersion, the filter cake was dried and pulled together with the Shota filter. The solubility is calculated by the following formula:[3]

$$solubility(\%) = \frac{m_1 - (m_3 - m_2)}{m_1} \cdot 100\%;$$

where m1- is the mass of the sample, g; m2 -is the mass of the empty filter, g; m3- is the mass of the filter with the sediment, g.

Table 1.

Methods for isolating beta-glucan polysaccharides and their influence on the monomeric composition

	Overall	Ara	Xyl	Glc	Ara/xyl	Glc/Ara	Glc/Xyl	Glc/AX	GAX/GA
Salt wat.	54,4	18,2	28,4	7,8	0,64	0,43	0,27	12,17	28,4
Dist.wat.	49,8	4,8	7,3	37,7	0,66	7,85	5,16	57,34	7,3

KOH	31,6	5,8	12,3	13,5	0,47	2,33	1,10	28,63	12,3
NaOH	15,1	2	4	9,1	0,50	4,55	2,28	18,20	4
SEF	9,8	2,30	2,20	5,30	1,05	2,30	2,41	5,07	2,2

Table shows that the solubility of isolated samples is significantly influenced by the type of monomeric glucoside units and their ratio. It is evident that among these units, the ratio of Arabinose and Xylose units to glucose units is the main factor influencing the water solubility factor. When this value was 57.34, the solubility of the samples in distilled water was the highest, reaching 12.5%.

Figure 1. Diagram of the influence of beta-glucan polysaccharide monomer composition on water solubility

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